

Antimicrobial and anti-nociceptive profile of some 4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-phenylazetidin-2-ones

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Abstract : A new series of 4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-phenylazetidin-2-ones (7a-j) were prepared by intermolecular cyclization of Schiff bases (6a-j) and mono chloro acetyl chloride in the presence of base catalyst triethyl amine. The biological evaluations of the compounds like antimicrobial, analgesic were performed. From the biological investigation it was found that out of all the synthesized compounds 1-(4-chlorophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7a), 1-(4-bromophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7b), 1-(3,4-dichlorophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7d), 1-(3,4-difluorophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7f), 1-(4-methoxyphenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7j) were shown potent antimicrobial and anti-nociceptive property compared to standards.

Keywords : Pyrazole-4-carboxaldehyde, azetidine-2-one, antimicrobial, analgesic.

Introduction

Pyrazole derivatives belong to five membered aromatic heterocyclic compounds. They attracted a great attention of medicinal chemists due to wide range of pharmacological activities associated with them. In particular, they were used as antitumor, antibacterial and antifungal, antiviral, antiparasitic, anti-tubercular and insecticidal agents. Some of these compounds also showed anti-inflammatory, anti-diabetic, anesthetic and analgesic properties¹. Another heterocyclic azoles azetidin-2-one, also known as β -lactam monocyclic ring, reported to exhibit interesting biological activities. Recently, some other types of biological activity besides the antibacterial activity also reported for azetidin-2-ones nucleus. Such biological activities include antimicrobial, anti-tubercular, carbonic anhydrase inhibitors, local anesthetics, anti-inflammatory, antihelminthic, anticonvulsant, hypoglycemic activity². The study showed that microbial infection induces inflammation through immune cell recruitment. Inflammatory pain during infection has been thought to be triggered by the action of immune-derived proteins (for example, cytokines and growth factors), lipids (for example, prostaglandins) and other mediators such as

amines, potassium and protons on receptors expressed by nociceptors³⁻⁵. Keeping these in mind, our present study was designed to synthesize some 4-(3-methyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-phenylazetidin-2-one moieties by cyclization of unsymmetrical imines in the presence of chloro acetyl chloride and a base catalyst to search potent compounds, which might have potency to overcome associated problem of microbial infection and pain.

Results and discussion

The Schiff's bases (6a-j) were obtained by the reaction between electrophilic carbon atom of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carbaldehyde (4) and nucleophilic nitrogen atom of substituted aromatic amines. The intermolecular 2+2 cyclization of unsymmetrical imines give formation of azetidine-2-one derivatives (7a-j). The reactions were proceeds in the presence of triethyl amine as base catalyst. Tertiary amine counter balances between nucleophilic character and basicity which was considered as key factor for efficient completion of reaction. The substitutions on aromatic amine have great significance on yield value. The substitution with electron donating group at *para* and *meta* position of ring increases per-

Scheme 1

centage yield where as it decreases in case of *ortho* substitution due to steric effect.

The physical and analytical data were recorded for synthesized compounds. The formations of desired compounds further were subjected for elemental analysis (C, H, N analysis). In view of establishment of structure spectral analysis was performed. The IR peaks in KBr pellets recorded at 1775.67–1692.61, 1685.73–1640.67, 1321.33–1260.33 and 1280.11–1150.11 cm^{-1} indicate

presence of C=O, C=N, C–N and C–C groups in synthesized compounds. The characteristic ^1H NMR peaks at 7.75–7.41, 4.85–4.81, 3.49–3.43 and 3.25–3.15 indicates presence of CH=N and azetidine-2-one nucleus in compounds **6a-j**, **7a-j** respectively. The ^{13}C NMR spectral data also give characteristic peak according to proposed structure. From the mass spectra it was found that mass peaks matches with calculated molecular mass of the synthesized compounds.

It has been reported that pyrazoline⁶⁻⁸ and 2-azetidinones² possess analgesic, anti-inflammatory and antimicrobial activities. Microbial infections produced pain by unknown molecular mechanisms, although they are presumed to be secondary to immune activation. Bacteria induce calcium flux and action potentials in nociceptor neurons via *N*-formylated peptides and the pore-forming toxin α -haemolysin, through distinct mechanisms. Specific ablation of Nav1.8-lineage neurons, which include nociceptors, abrogated pain during bacterial infection concurrently increased local immune infiltration and lymphadenopathy of the draining lymph node. Thus, bacterial pathogens produce pain by directly activating sensory neurons that modulate inflammation, an unsuspected role for the nervous system in host pathogen interactions⁹. Based on this fact, present study was aimed to investigate the antimicrobial and anti-nociceptive property of the some novel pyrazoline derivative, where beta lactam rings present. The antimicrobial activity was determined by paper disc diffusion technique against different strains of bacteria and fungi at 100 μ g, 150 μ g, and 250 μ g/ml shown in the Table 1. From the antimicrobial data (zone of inhibition) it was found that compounds **7a**, **7b**, **7d**, **7f** and **7j** were showing more antimicrobial activity compare to standards, whereas compound **7e**, **7j** and **7i** have shown moderate activity. The compounds were able to exhibit antibacterial activity probably by inhibition of cell wall synthesis due to presence of beta lactam rings¹⁰, but antifungal activity associated might be due to azole nucleus by inhibiting ergosterol biosynthesis¹¹. The analgesic activity of the synthesized compounds (**7a-j**) were determined by the acetic acid-induced mouse writhing tests (Table 2), tail flick (Table 3), tail immersion (Table 4) and by the formalin-induced pain method (Table 5). It is well established that thermal nociceptive tests are more sensitive to opioid μ -agonists and non-thermal tests to opioid κ -agonists¹². Aspirin produces analgesia through inhibition of prostaglandin synthesis. The abdominal contraction response induced by acetic acid used for peripherally acting analgesics and such a response was thought to involve local peritoneal receptors. The tail immersion and tail flick tests caused a profound and dose related analgesia in the treated mice, which are behavioural methods that have been developed to study nociception in ani-

Table 1. *In vitro* antimicrobial study by disc diffusion technique of compounds **7a-j**

Compd.	Gram-positive bacteria						Gram-negative bacteria						Fungus					
	<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>			<i>Bacillus subtilis</i>			<i>Escherichia coli</i>			<i>Enterobacter cloacae</i>			<i>Aspergillus niger</i>			<i>Candida albicans</i>		
	100 (μ g/ml)	150 (μ g/ml)	250 (μ g/ml)	100 (μ g/ml)	150 (μ g/ml)	250 (μ g/ml)	100 (μ g/ml)	150 (μ g/ml)	250 (μ g/ml)	100 (μ g/ml)	150 (μ g/ml)	250 (μ g/ml)	100 (μ g/ml)	150 (μ g/ml)	250 (μ g/ml)	100 (μ g/ml)	150 (μ g/ml)	250 (μ g/ml)
7a	10	13	15	11	13	15	18	20	20.5	10.6	13	15	9	10.5	13	10	12	15
7b	11	16	18	11	13.5	16	17	19	21	11.5	16	18	11	13	15	11	14	15
7c	11	13	15	17	16.1	18	19.8	22	23.2	16.1	19	21	16	17	18	16	18	19
7d	15	18	20	18	15	19	21	22	24	15	18	20	15	17	18.3	15	17	19
7e	13	14	15	11	13	17	13	13.6	15	12.4	13	15	10	14	17	10	14	16
7f	14	18	20	14	13	18	17	19	21	17	18	20	14	16	18	14	16	19
7g	11	12	16	13	13	15	18	20	23	10	13	15	12	13	18	10	16	15
7h	11	13	15	12	12	15	19	20	23	10	13	15	11	12	18	10	16	15
7i	13	15	19	13	13	14	18	20	23	12	13	17	13	17	18	10	12	15
7j	11	18	19	11	11.2	20	19	21	22.7	15	18	19	11	14	17	11	14	18
Amoxicillin	10	12	14.1	12	14	17.1	13	18	22.1	12	14	17.1	-	-	-	-	-	-
Streptomycin	11	13	16	11	13	16	19	21	22	11	13	16	-	-	-	-	-	-
Nystatin	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	-	10	13.5	16	10	13.5	16

Table 2. Analgesic activity – Effect of compounds **7a-j** on mice by Writhing tests

Treatment (i.p.) (mg/kg)	Mean response without drug (s)	No of writhing		
		After 30 min	After 60 min	After 90 min
Control (0.2 ml/kg)	32.60 ± 0.012	32.76 ± 0.04	33.81 ± 0.07	32.81 ± 0.07
Aspirin (100)	53.30 ± 0.09	45.87 ± 0.01	38.69 ± 0.18***	24.19 ± 0.18***
7a (50)	56.60 ± 0.018	48.77 ± 0.04	41.66 ± 0.11***	26.16 ± 0.11***
7b (50)	53.04 ± 0.19	49.86 ± 0.07	42.84 ± 0.15**	22.24 ± 0.15***
7c (50)	52.31 ± 0.13	41.31 ± 0.20	34.36 ± 0.18	30.16 ± 0.18
7d (50)	47.13 ± 0.09	38.22 ± 0.18	27.14 ± 0.22***	19.24 ± 0.22***
7e (50)	35.57 ± 0.11	29.15 ± 0.13	21.13 ± 0.16	10.18 ± 0.15**
7f (50)	52.14 ± 0.07	48.02 ± 0.05	39.95 ± 0.12***	25.45 ± 0.12***
7g (50)	38.16 ± 0.07	33.03 ± 0.13	26.96 ± 0.21	21.56 ± 0.21**
7h (50)	31.69 ± 0.18	28.22 ± 0.18	29.69 ± 0.18	25.49 ± 0.18
7i (50)	52.04 ± 0.19	48.87 ± 0.21	47.04 ± 0.22**	46.04 ± 0.22**
7j (50)	58.04 ± 0.19	49.27 ± 0.21	39.04 ± 0.22***	36.12 ± 0.22***

Table 3. Analgesic activity – Effect of Compounds **7a-j** on mice by Tail clip test for mice

Treatment (i.p.) (mg/kg)	Mean response without drug (s)	Mean reaction response (s)		
		After 30 min	After 60 min	After 90 min
Control (0.2 ml/kg)	22.66 ± 0.012	22.76 ± 0.04	22.81 ± 0.07	24.81 ± 0.07
Morphine (5)	22.36 ± 0.09	25.87 ± 0.21	29.69 ± 0.18***	36.19 ± 0.18***
7a (50)	21.69 ± 0.018	28.77 ± 0.05	31.66 ± 0.11***	43.16 ± 0.11***
7b (50)	23.04 ± 0.19	29.86 ± 0.07	34.84 ± 0.15***	48.24 ± 0.15***
7c (50)	24.31 ± 0.13	30.30 ± 0.2	33.26 ± 0.18	35.26 ± 0.18
7d (50)	25.03 ± 0.09	32.22 ± 0.18	36.14 ± 0.22***	43.24 ± 0.22***
7e (50)	24.57 ± 0.11	29.15 ± 0.13	31.13 ± 0.16	32.18 ± 0.15
7f (50)	26.14 ± 0.07	32.02 ± 0.05	39.95 ± 0.12***	44.45 ± 0.12***
7g (50)	25.16 ± 0.07	29.03 ± 0.13	33.96 ± 0.21***	42.56 ± 0.21***
7h (50)	21.69 ± 0.18	28.22 ± 0.18	29.69 ± 0.18*	33.49 ± 0.18***
7i (50)	22.04 ± 0.19	28.87 ± 0.21	34.14 ± 0.22	42.04 ± 0.22**
7j (50)	23.04 ± 0.19	31.27 ± 0.21	36.14 ± 0.22	47.12 ± 0.22***

mals¹³. The data generated in the present study suggests that the involvement of both κ and μ opioid receptor are distinct in the analgesic activity of compounds. The formalin-induced pain as an experimental model of analgesia is useful for elucidating mechanism of pain and analgesia. Drugs that act centrally, such as the narcotics inhibit both phases of formalin-induced pain, while peripherally acting drugs can only inhibit the late phase¹⁴. From the result it was found that compounds **7a**, **7b**, **7d**, **7h** and **7j** were showing more potent analgesic activity compare to standards (aspirin and morphine sulphate) due to attachment of groups at *para* position on phenyl ring, whereas bisubstitution at *para* and *meta* substituted com-

pounds **7d**, **7f** have shown moderate activity compared to standard drugs. From the above discussion, it was confirmed that presence of azetidine-2-one nucleus along with pyrazole nucleus increase the potency of compounds. However in particular, efficacy depends on substitution at phenyl ring, which was attached to azetidine-2-one nucleus. Compounds with *para* substitution are potent, where as bisubstituted compounds at *para* and *meta* position showed moderate activity. The *ortho* substituted compounds were not able to show significant activity. It was also observed that electron withdrawing substituents at *para* or *meta* position decrease the potency of compounds.

Table 4. Analgesic activity – Effect of compounds **7a-j** on mice by hot immersion method

Treatment (i.p.) (mg/kg)	Mean response without drug (s)	Mean reaction response (s)		
		After 30 min	After 60 min	After 90 min
Control (0.2 ml/kg)	2.66 ± 0.012	2.76 ± 0.04	2.81 ± 0.07	2.88 ± 0.07
Morphine (5)	2.36 ± 0.09	3.87 ± 0.21***	5.69 ± 0.18***	8.69 ± 0.17***
7a (50)	1.69 ± 0.018	2.77 ± 0.05***	4.66 ± 0.11***	7.64 ± 0.11***
7b (50)	2.04 ± 0.19	2.86 ± 0.07***	5.84 ± 0.15***	8.34 ± 0.15***
7c (50)	2.31 ± 0.13	3.3 ± 0.21	3.86 ± 0.18	4.56 ± 0.18
7d (50)	2.03 ± 0.09	3.22 ± 0.18***	5.14 ± 0.22***	9.24 ± 0.22***
7e (50)	2.27 ± 0.11	3.15 ± 0.13	4.33 ± 0.16**	8.73 ± 0.16**
7f (50)	2.14 ± 0.07	3.02 ± 0.05**	4.95 ± 0.12***	8.95 ± 0.12***
7g (50)	2.16 ± 0.07	3.03 ± 0.13**	3.96 ± 0.21***	9.96 ± 0.21***
7h (50)	2.69 ± 0.18	3.22 ± 0.18	4.01 ± 0.18	5.21 ± 0.18
7i (50)	2.04 ± 0.19	3.87 ± 0.21***	5.64 ± 0.22**	8.24 ± 0.22**
7j (50)	2.34 ± 0.19	3.97 ± 0.21***	5.14 ± 0.22**	9.64 ± 0.22***

After immersion in water at 55 °C.

Table 5. Effect of compounds **7a-j** on Phase-1 and Phase-2 by formalin induced analgesia

Treatment (i.p.) (mg/kg)	Mean response without drug (s)	Time spent in licking paw	
		0–5 min	15–30 min
Control (0.2 ml/kg)	132.60 ± 0.01	135.76 ± 0.04	133.21 ± 0.07
Morphine (5)	142.41 ± 0.14	15.27 ± 0.01***	16.19 ± 0.18***
Aspirin (100)	135.60 ± 0.11	85.87 ± 0.31***	89.69 ± 0.18***
7a (50)	138.28 ± 0.01	48.27 ± 0.24***	70.66 ± 0.11***
7b (50)	131.34 ± 0.21	59.86 ± 0.27***	71.84 ± 0.15
7c (50)	135.61 ± 0.11	87.30 ± 0.21	88.26 ± 0.18***
7d (50)	132.63 ± 0.21	68.22 ± 0.18***	76.14 ± 0.22***
7e (50)	133.20 ± 0.31	79.15 ± 0.13***	81.13 ± 0.16***
7f (50)	137.63 ± 0.21	58.02 ± 0.05**	55.95 ± 0.12***
7g (50)	138.65 ± 0.01	83.03 ± 0.13**	86.96 ± 0.21***
7h (50)	135.60 ± 0.21	87.22 ± 0.18	89.69 ± 0.18
7i (50)	131.11 ± 0.11	79.87 ± 0.21***	84.04 ± 0.22**
7j (50)	132.20 ± 0.01	68.27 ± 0.21***	73.14 ± 0.22***

Experimental

General :

All the chemicals used for the synthesis were of reagent grade of Sigma Aldrich and Merck Laboratory. The solvents were purified by standard laboratory procedure and free from atmospheric oxygen. The melting points of synthesized compounds were determined by open capillary method and were not corrected. The IR spectra were recorded in KBr pellets on a Shimadzu 8201 PC FTIR spectrophotometer. Both ¹H and ¹³C NMR were recorded in DMSO-*d*₆ by using Bruker 500 MHz-NMR

spectrophotometers using TMS as internal standard. The masses of the compounds were analyzed by ESI-mass method using Thermo Finnigan mass spectrophotometer. Elemental analyses were observed by using Thermo Finnigan FLASH EA 1112 CHN analyzer. TLC was performed in pre-coated plastic sheet of silica gel g/UV-254 of 0.2 mm thickness.

Chemistry :

General procedure for synthesis of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,2-dihydropyrazol-5-one (3) :

108 g, 1 mole of phenyl hydrazine was taken in 500

ml beaker. 130 g, 1 mole equivalent of ethyl aceto acetate was added and allowed to warm the mixture at 100 °C on water bath for 3 h. Cooling of the mixture at room temperature resulted solidification of crystal. Washing was taken place with ether and recrystallized from hot ethanol¹⁵. Yield : 93%; m.p. 193–194 °C; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ /ppm) : 7.18 (5H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 5.18 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 2.15 (1H, s, -NH- of pyrazole), 1.17 (3H, s, -CH₃ of pyrazole).

General procedure for synthesis of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carboxaldehyde (4) :

174.2 g of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1,2-dihydropyrazol-5-one (3) taken in round bottom flask and to that 219.27 g, 3 mole of DMF and 153 g, 1 mole of POCl₃ were added. During addition of POCl₃ the temperature of reaction mixture was maintained 0–5 °C under nitrogen atmosphere. After completion of addition the mixture was refluxed for 6 h. Then sodium hydroxide was added and cooled for overnight. Addition of crushed ice further, formation of precipitation was taken place and then recrystallized from hot ethanol¹⁶. Yield : 83%; m.p. 146–147 °C; ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ /ppm) : 8.52 (1H, s, -CHO of pyrazole), 7.82 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 7.31 (5H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 2.79 (3H, s, -CH₃ of pyrazole).

General procedure for synthesis of N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (6a-j) :

The reaction mixture of 2 g of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazole-4-carboxaldehyde (4) in 50 ml of ethanol was stirred for 30 min under nitrogen atmosphere. Added 1 ml of glacial acetic acid followed by addition of 2 g of substituent aromatic amines and refluxed for 1 h. On addition of crushed ice, precipitation was taken place and then filtered, dried at room temperature and then recrystallized from hot ethanol¹⁷.

4-Chloro-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (6a) :

Yield : 93%; m.p. 85–86 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2955.34 (-CH₃, str.), 1450.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1671.67 (C=N, str.), 664.21 (C-Cl, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ /ppm) : 7.52 (1H, s, -N=CH- of imines), 7.31 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.2–7.18 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.8–6.78 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 2.74 (3H, s, -CH₃ of

pyrazole).

4-Bromo-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (6b) :

Yield : 92%; m.p. 83–85 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2950.52 (-CH₃, str.), 1469.35 (-CH₃, def.), 1624.73 (C=N, str.), 621.93 (C-Br, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ /ppm) : 7.49 (1H, s, -N=CH- of imine), 7.21 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.17–7.15 (2H, d, *J* 5 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.12 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.82–6.70 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 2.75 (3H, s, -CH₃ of pyrazole).

4-Nitro-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (6c) :

Yield : 87%; m.p. 95–97 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2953.52 (-CH₃, str.), 1685.73 (C=N, str.), 1540.02 (C-NO₂, str.), 1450.35 (-CH₃, def.).

3,4-Dichloro-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (6d) :

Yield : 88%; m.p. 83–84 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2927.14 (-CH₃, str.), 1434.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1679.67 (C=N, str.), 764.21 (C-Cl, str.).

4-Chloro-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-3-nitrobenzenimine (6e) :

Yield : 78%; m.p. 93–94 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2927.34 (-CH₃, str.), 1515.02 (C-NO₂, str.), 1436.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1683.67 (C=N, str.), 764.21 (C-Cl, str.).

3,4-Difluoro-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (6f) :

Yield : 68%; m.p. 81–82 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2925.14 (-CH₃, str.), 1534.34 (C-NO₂, str.), 1432.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1681.67 (C=N, str.), 1363.21 (C-F, str.).

2-Fluoro-N-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-5-nitrobenzenimine (6g) :

Yield : 79%; m.p. 93–94 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2927.14 (-CH₃, str.), 1534.34 (C-NO₂, str.), 1433.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1680.67 (C=N, str.), 1160.21 (C-F, str.).

N-((3-Methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-4-(trifluoromethyl)-benzenimine (6h) :

Yield : 95%; m.p. 101–102 °C; IR (KBr, ν_{\max} /cm⁻¹) : 2937.14 (-CH₃, str.), 1430.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1670.67 (C=N, str.), 1136.21 (C-F, str.).

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N-((3-Methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-4-nitro-3-(trifluoromethyl)-benzenimine (**6i**) :

Yield : 78%; m.p. 108–110 °C; IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2935.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1413.02 (C-NO₂, str.), 1640.67 (C=N, str.), 1336.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1330.21 (C-F, str.).

4-Methoxy-*N*-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimine (**6j**) :

Yield : 78%; m.p. 95–96 °C; IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2824.14 (-CH₃, str.), 2815.22 (-OCH₃, str.), 1432.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1683.67 (C=N, str.).

Synthesis of 4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-phenylazetidin-2-one (**7a-j**) :

The 2 g of *N*-((3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-methylene)-benzenimines were placed in 100 ml round bottom flask and stirred under nitrogen atmosphere followed by addition of 1,4-dioxan (20 ml) as solvent. Triethyl amine was used as base catalyst (0.5 ml) and stirred for 1 h. The resulting solutions were cooled at 0–5 °C and added 2 ml of chloro acetyl chloride. During addition of chloro acetyl chloride internal temperature was maintained not more than 8 °C. Reflux the mixture for 8 h and cool at room temperature for overnight. The mixtures were neutralized with 5% sodium bicarbonate solution after addition of ice. The compounds were washed with cold water and 50% ethyl acetate in petroleum ether and then dried. The purification of compounds was carried out by using benzene and chloroform as mobile phase in column chromatographic technique.

1-(4-Chlorophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (**7a**) :

Yield : 68%; m.p. 131–132 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) C₁₉H₁₆ClN₃O : C, 67.56 (67.36); H, 4.77 (4.49); N, 12.44 (12.22); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2959.34 (-CH₃, str.), 1775.67 (C=O, str.), 1455.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1260.33 (C-N, str.), 1200.11 (C-C, str.), 760.21 (C-Cl, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 7.33 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.2–7.18 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.8–6.78 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.85 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.49 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.24 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 2.74 (3H, s, -CH₃ of pyrazole); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500

MHz, δ/ppm) : 170.9, 147.1, 145.5, 141.4, 139.7, 132.8, 131.4, 130.2, 130.2, 129.4, 129.4, 126.3, 123.7, 123.7, 120.2, 105, 45, 45, 11; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 337.17 (M⁺).

1-(4-Bromophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (**7b**) :

Yield : 66%; m.p. 133–134 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₁₃H₁₂BrN₃O : C, 59.70 (59.46); H, 4.22 (3.99); N, 10.99 (10.52); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2953.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1692.61 (C=O, str.), 1463.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1310.33 (C-N, str.), 1180.11 (C-C, str.), 667.21 (C-Br, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 7.31 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.21–7.19 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.17 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.81–6.79 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.81 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.47 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.22 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 2.70 (3H, s, -CH₃ of pyrazole); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 171.9, 147.2, 146.5, 142.4, 139.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.1, 130.1, 129.3, 129.3, 126.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 105.3, 45.1, 45.1, 11; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 381.02 (M⁺).

4-(3-Methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(4-nitrophenyl)azetidin-2-one (**7c**) :

Yield : 76%; m.p. 128–129 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₁₉H₁₆N₄O₃ : C, 65.51 (65.40); H, 4.63 (4.49); N, 16.08 (15.82); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2949.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1701.61 (C=O, str.), 1525.02 (C-NO₂, str.), 1461.34 (-CH₃, def.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1182.11 (C-C, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 7.31 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.21–7.21 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.82–6.80 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.85 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.43 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.22 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 171.3, 147.1, 146.3, 141.4, 138.5, 132.5, 131.4, 130.5, 130.5, 129.5, 129.5, 127.7, 124.8, 124.8, 120.1, 105.3, 45.3, 45.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 348.19 (M⁺).

1-(3,4-Dichlorophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1*H*-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (**7d**) :

Yield : 68%; m.p. 110–111 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₁₉H₁₅Cl₂N₃O : C, 61.30 (60.88);

H, 4.06 (3.99); N, 11.29 (11.00); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 2948.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1720.61 (C=O, str.), 1471.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1180.11 (C-C, str.), 764.21 (C-Cl, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.45 (1H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.33 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.25 (1H, s of pyrazole), 7.2–7.18 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.11–7.09 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.83 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.41 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.22 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 170.3, 146.1, 143.3, 141.2, 133.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.2, 130.2, 129.5, 129.5, 126.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 108.3, 47.3, 47.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*): 371.15 (M⁺).

1-(4-Chloro-3-nitrophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7e) :

Yield : 63%; m.p. 119–120 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₁₉H₁₅ClN₄O₃ : C, 59.61 (59.40); H, 3.95 (3.55); N, 14.64 (14.91); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 2948.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1720.61 (C=O, str.), 1525.02 (C-NO₂, str.), 1471.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1180.11 (C-C, str.), 764.21 (C-Cl, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.43 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.35 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 7.26–7.24 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.2–7.18 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.09 (1H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.85 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.49 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.25 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 2.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 170.3, 146.1, 143.3, 141.2, 133.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.2, 130.2, 129.5, 129.5, 126.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 108.3, 47.3, 47.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*): 382.08 (M⁺).

1-(3,4-Difluorophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7f) :

Yield : 63%; m.p. 123–124 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₁₉H₁₅F₂N₃O : C, 67.25 (67.11); H, 4.46 (4.22); N, 12.38 (12.11); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 2948.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1720.61 (C=O, str.), 1471.14 (-CH₃, def.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1201 (C-F, str.), 1180.11 (C-C, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, δ/ppm): 7.32 (1H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.29 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.23–7.21 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.11–7.09 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 6.99 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of pyrazole), 4.83 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one),

3.48 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.15 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 171.3, 145.1, 143.7, 141.3, 135.5, 133.7, 131.8, 130.2, 130.2, 127.5, 127.5, 125.7, 121.8, 121.8, 120.1, 108.3, 45.3, 45.3, 11.4; ESI-MS (*m/z*): 339.12 (M⁺).

1-(2-Fluoro-5-nitrophenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (7g) :

Yield : 69%; m.p. 131–132 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₁₉H₁₅FN₄O₃ : C, 62.29 (62.11); H, 4.12 (3.96); N, 15.29 (14.90); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 2927.14 (-CH₃, str.), 1720.61 (C=O, str.), 1534.34 (C-NO₂, str.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1433.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1280.11 (C-C, str.), 1160.21 (C-F, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 8.2–8.18 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.92–7.90 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.45 (1H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.39 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.21–7.19 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of pyrazole), 4.81 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.43 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.15 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 170.3, 146.1, 143.3, 141.2, 133.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.2, 130.2, 129.5, 129.5, 126.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 108.3, 47.3, 47.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*): 366.11 (M⁺).

4-(3-Methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(4-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)azetidin-2-one (7h) :

Yield : 65%; m.p. 125–127 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₂₀H₁₆F₃N₃O : C, 64.69 (64.42); H, 4.34 (4.11); N, 11.32 (11.19); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$): 2927.14 (-CH₃, str.), 1720.61 (C=O, str.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1433.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1150.11 (C-C, str.), 1160.21 (C-F, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 7.33 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.21–7.18 (2H, d, *J* 15 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.8–6.78 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.81 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.43 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.15 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm): 170.3, 146.1, 143.3, 141.2, 133.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.2, 130.2, 129.5, 129.5, 126.7, 124.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 108.3, 47.3, 47.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*): 371.12 (M⁺).

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4-(3-Methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)-1-(4-nitro-3-(trifluoromethyl)phenyl)azetidin-2-one (**7i**) :

Yield : 88%; m.p. 128–129 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₂₀H₁₅F₃N₄O₃ : C, 57.69 (57.25); H, 3.63 (3.46); N, 13.47 (13.17); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2925.24 (-CH₃, str.), 1720.61 (C=O, str.), 1513.02 (C-NO₂, str.), 1436.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1330.21 (C-F, str.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1200.11 (C-C, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 8.12–8.10 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.7 (1H, s, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.62–7.60 (1H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.41 (5H, s of phenyl), 6.85 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 2.39 (3H, s, -CH₃), 4.81 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.43 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.15 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 2.39 (3H, s, -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 170.3, 146.1, 143.3, 141.2, 133.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.2, 130.2, 129.5, 129.5, 126.7, 124.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 108.3, 47.3, 47.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 416.07 (M⁺).

1-(4-Methoxyphenyl)-4-(3-methyl-1-phenyl-1H-pyrazol-4-yl)azetidin-2-one (**7j**) :

Yield : 78%; m.p. 117–118 °C; Elemental analysis Calcd. (Found) for C₂₀H₁₉N₃O₂ : C, 72.06 (71.86); H, 5.78 (5.52); N, 12.60 (12.48); IR (KBr, $\nu_{\max}/\text{cm}^{-1}$) : 2924.14 (-CH₃, str.), 2855.22 (-OCH₃), 1730.21 (C=O, str.), 1432.24 (-CH₃, def.), 1321.33 (C-N, str.), 1200.11 (C-C, str.); ¹H NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 7.37 (5H, s of phenyl), 7.21–7.19 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 7.15 (1H, s, Ar-H of pyrazole), 6.8–6.78 (2H, d, *J* 10 Hz, Ar-H of phenyl), 4.81 (1H, s, CH-N of azetidin-2-one), 3.43 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.15 (1H, s, CH₂-C=O of azetidin-2-one), 3.73 (3H, s of -CH₃); ¹³C NMR (DMSO-*d*₆, 500 MHz, δ/ppm) : 170.3, 146.1, 143.3, 141.2, 133.5, 132.7, 131.3, 130.2, 130.2, 129.5, 129.5, 126.7, 124.7, 123.8, 123.8, 120.1, 108.3, 55.1, 47.3, 47.3, 11.1; ESI-MS (*m/z*) : 333.17 (M⁺).

Biological activity :

Test microorganism and medium :

For the determination of antimicrobial activity Gram-positive bacteria *Staphylococcus aureas* ATCC12600, *Bacillus subtilis* ATCC 11775, *Enterobacter cloacae* ATCC13047 and the fungi *Candida albicans* ATCC 90028, *Aspergillus niger* ATCC1027 were used. Bacte-

rial strains were cultured overnight at 37 °C in LB-agar broth and fungal strains were cultured over night at 30 °C in cornmeal agar media. Test strains were suspended in nutrient agar to give final density of 5 × 10⁵ cfu/ ml.

Screening for antimicrobial activity (zone of inhibition assay) :

Antimicrobial activity of the compounds was determined by disc diffusion method¹⁸. Sterilized 10% nutrient agar (20 ml) was poured into each sterile Petri dish after mixing the culture of micro-organism at the concentration of 150 µL and allowed to solidify the plate. Standard and test compounds were dissolved in DMSO to make a stock solution of 1000 µg/ml. From the stock solution concentration of 100, 150, 200 µg/ml made for amoxicillin, streptomycin, nystatin and test compounds **7(a-j)** respectively. Wattmann filter paper was sterilized and dipped in test compounds, standards and solvent control respectively. Discs were placed on agar plates and incubated at 37 °C for 24 h for bacterial and 30 °C for 24 h for fungi and the zone of inhibition was determined in millimeter. Each study was performed in triplicate.

Animals :

Albino mice of either sex weighing between 18–25 g were taken for analgesic activity. Animals were maintained under standard environmental condition at temperature of 22 ± 2 °C and 45–50% relative humidity for 24 h each of dark and light cycle with proper diet. All the studies were done according to protocol approved by Institutional Animal Ethical Committee (IAEC) of Bansal College of Pharmacy (Reg. no. 1252/ac/10/CPCSEA, Ref. no. BCP/IAEC/12/02).

Acute toxicity study :

The acute oral toxicity study was carried out according to OECD guideline no. 423 in albino mice¹⁹. The doses were fixed at 10 mg/kg (p.o) to 100 mg/kg (p.o) and contain 5 in each group. The mortality and general behaviors were under observation for 14 days. The test compounds were nontoxic in the dose of 50 mg/kg body weight.

Analgesic activity :

Writhing tests :

Mice of either sex with a weight between 20 and 25 g are used. 0.1 ml of a 0.6% solution of acetic acid is

injected intraperitoneally to mice^{20,21}. The animals were consisted of 12 groups, 5 in each group. Group-1 was considered as control, Group-2 was used for morphine sulfate (5 mg/kg) as standard and Group-3 to 12 were used for test compounds (**7a-j**). The mice were placed individually into glass beakers and five min are allowed to elapse. The mice were then observed for a period of ten min and the number of writhes was recorded for each animal. The time period with the greatest percent of inhibition is considered the peak time. A dose range is reserved for interesting compounds or those which inhibit writhing more than 70%. Compounds with less than 70% inhibition were considered to have minimal activity.

Haffner's tail clip :

Male albino mice with a weight between 18 and 25 g were used. The animals were consisted of 12 groups 5 in each group. Group-1 was considered as control, Group-2 was used for morphine sulfate (5 mg/kg) as standard and Group-3 to 12 were used for test compounds (**7a-j**). The test compounds were administered 15 min prior testing. An artery clip²² was applied to the root of the tail approximately 1 cm from the body to induce pain. The animal quickly responds to this noxious stimulus by biting the clip. The reaction time of the test animals which were greater than the cut-off time is called a positive response indicate presence of analgesic activity. The length of time until response indicates the period of greatest activity after dosing.

Tail immersion test :

Young albino mice of either sex 25–30 g were used for study²³. The animals were consisted of 12 groups 5 in each group. Group-1 was considered as control, Group-2 was used for morphine sulfate (5 mg/kg) as standard drug and Group-3 to 12 were used for test compounds. The animals allowed to adopt the environment before study the tails were marked 5 cm above and immersed in hot water of exactly 55 °C. The tail withdrawal time was noted down before and after administration of drug in sec. The cut of time is 10 s and 1–5 s for treated and untreated animals respectively. If tail withdrawal time is more than 6 s, indicates positive response.

Formalin test :

Formalin test was done by the method of Hunkskaer *et al.*²⁴. The animals were consisted of 12 groups 5 in each

group. Group-1 was considered as control, Group-2 and 3 were used for aspirin (100 mg/kg) and morphine sulfate (5 mg/kg) as standard and Group-4 to 13 were used for test compounds (**6a-j**). After 30 min treatment of all tested compounds (15 min treatment for morphine), 20 µL of 2.5% formalin was injected subcutaneously in hind paw of rats. The time spent in licking the injected paw in early phase (0–5 min) and late phase (15–30 min) was recorded.

Statistical analysis :

The results were shown as Mean \pm SEM and comparison between standard and test compounds were made by one way ANOVA followed by Dunnetts test. Values of $p \leq 0.001$ were considered as significant.

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